

EXTREME UNCERTAINTY AND FEELING OF BEING ROUNDED–UP 360 DEGREES: BECOME A PHOENIX USING CONCEPTS OF MERGED TIME PERSPECTIVE AND REFLECTIVE SELF-LIMITING

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ABSTRACT

Individuals come across extreme Uncertainty situations, feeling rounded–up 360 degrees, as if trapped inside Chakra Vyuha (wheel form strategy). For uncertainty is often related to future, the concept of Future Time perspective (FTP) is relied upon for attaining positive states. But FTP is a critical factor which works both positively and negatively depending on other factors intervening. For politicians and businessmen such states of being trapped in Chakra Vyuha, can mean end of their political life or business life. In the current paper, the author describes the introspection of a Subject while he attempted to alter his Future Time perspective. This introspective report further gave clue for Merged Time Perspective or Seamless Time Horizon instead of FTP and also that Regulatory Focus and Resistance To Change need to be combined, coalesced and treated on a single continuum. Current author also has proposed a therapy outline to help businessmen and politicians to come out of devastating situations in which they feel rounded – up by opponents 360 degrees.

Keywords: *Merged Time perspective, Seamless Time Horizon, Reflective Self– Limiting, Extreme Uncertainty, Rounded – Up / Blocked 360 degree*

1. WHY THIS ATTEMPT?

Probably uncertainty was the earliest creation of nature when the world was created and living organisms began to have ‘some sort of mind’. Uncertainty is more important for both Economists and Psychologists because, the spot where these two converge is the *Business Growth*. Iván Bélyácz and Katalin Daubner, (2021), narrates the views of Taleb. He argued that no one can have complete insulation from uncertainty. This may be the reason why uncertainty is thought to be controlled by super-human powers / God.

In business, the possible solution for tackling uncertainty rested with robustness of one’s enterprise, economics (or theory of economics), and social institutions. Though such robust entities cannot guarantee one’s economic growth but can help to tackle or resist uncertainty and avoid harmful outcomes.

Psychologically, the ability to “build” such robust entities rests with the cognitive functions of the individual or individuals that may be selected to run the business. Economics has the power to prescribe but often implemented or moderated or mediated or nullified by psychological profile of the individuals involved. It has been suggested that when the decision makers face failure of actual choices, their uncertainty goes up. When the uncertainty is surrounding an individual from 360 degrees or if the individual perceives so, then he will be perceiving a bleak future even nearest in time, if not distant future. This is exactly the situation of a person surrounded by his opponents in a Chakra Vyuha (being rounded – up / blocked 360 degrees by others). Extreme of uncertainty and mostly in the nearest future is perceived when one is trapped and surrounded by opponents in a Chakra Vyuha.

But a businessman cannot attribute things entirely to external factors or economic climate and sit back. Businessmen and even politicians have the highest responsibility, when compared to people in other walks of life, of “steering the boat safe while the wind blows opposite”. Recent, Sri Lankan Economic Crisis, Shiv Sena party crisis of Maharashtra state and the sensitive religious issues – all remind us the politicians’ life situations. Similarly, business crises that cornered the well-known CEOs (Example, Vijay Mallya). This is where the businessmen and politicians claim the differentiated stress from others. Businessmen and politicians have this curse or boon, as they are ought to spend each moment, spell each word, and spend each paise (or dollar/penny), make each move, strategically uncompromisingly. Often the situation is that oneself surrounded from all sides as in ‘Chakra Vyuha’(being rounded – up / blocked). In being caught within ‘Chakra Vyuha’ the uncertainty is highest and closest in time (i.e every second one is alive)

Individuals do respond and show their survival instinct. The possible calculations associated with risk makes one more certain or at least less uncertain. This intermediate feel is subjective but universal. However, there is no exact measure to address this intermediate feel between more certain and less uncertain. Psychologists know that this kind of junctures are the hot seat of resistances or stagnations. On the other hand, the uncertainty is entirely vague without any measurable portion and unpredictable nature. Probably, the factor of “intermediate feel” is also the fertile ground for this uncertainty, once ‘extended’ or ‘increased’.

Here, the 'extended', is a factor pertains to *time perception* and 'increased', is a factor pertains to *volume perception*. Said 'volume' perceived by an individual could be so much that the total life perceived as 'lost' (uncertainty colours complete future events, actions, life style and outcomes). This is also the instance of 'perception of progress' in operation as differentiated from reward and the current author demonstrated in an experiment in his class that, students when lose perception of progress are not motivated to put efforts even though the assured rewards are increased (Ramesh Kumar, G S, 1999).

Time aspect, that plays a part in uncertainty, also influences the volume or perception. For example, an interview result delayed for a week's time could make the candidate feel uncertain limitedly; the same limited uncertainty increases in volume once the time extends beyond couple of months and he loses total hope, perceiving more uncertainty as he again has to try for a job from scratch and wait for interview results, then the salary negotiation and then the first salary after he meets one month's expenses.

1.1 Time Perspective and Uncertainty:

Time perspective is a factor which mentioned in literatures that help attain positive states. Future Time Perspective (FTP) could be used as predictive factors, to predict outcomes in educational, work, and health domains. More specifically FTP is strongly linked to educational outcomes (information / knowledge seeking and applying) than a more general FTP (Andre L, van Vianen AEM, Peetsma TTD, Oort FJ.,2018).

Time Perspective (TP) (Zimbardo, P. G., & Boyd, J. N.1999) is a concept of how one perceives his past, present and future. TPs are not mere concepts but have biological markers too. Zhiyi Chen, Yiqun Guo, Tingyong Feng (2018) found selective neural basis underlying TPs, and further provide the stable biomarkers for multidimensional TPs.

Whether Time Perspectives directly affect the success or in collaboration with other factors, is an area requiring further work. However, there are certain factors that align with Time Perspectives and other outcomes.

Witowska, Joanna and Zajenkowski, Marcin (2021) found two of the time perspectives - Past Positive and Present Fatalism, were significantly associated with Working Memory updating whereas switching showed no correlations with TPs. Working Memory is more closely relevant to one's success. For example, Salar Khanbabaei, Mohammad Hossein Abdollahi, Mahnaz Shahgholian,(2022) found that when working memory is enhanced, addictive tendencies decrease. The dimensions of TPs are also thus dichotomous in general – benign and malign. But this division depends more on how the individual balances each dimension rather than the dimension per se.

Time Perspective has major role in our mental health and how we function in a given situation. Anxiety patients are prone to systematic biases in all time perspective dimensions, particularly negative past and negative future time perspective. Applying the earlier concepts of current author (Ramesh Kumar G S 1999), the 'essence' being (i) the *time* (time-related events/outcomes) seen as opponent to oneself and (ii) the specific time that is not under one's own control (past is lost and future is uncertain) – these two combined in the thoughts based on the *association principle* of 'congruency' in thinking. Negative past and negative future time perspectives also correlate with worry and rumination, convincing Åström E, Seif A, Wiberg B, and Carelli M, G (2018) that interventions targeting temporal focus could reduce repetitive negative thinking. In other words, changing the views of the individual helps change his pathology, or improve performance.

TPs are so sensitive (at least not as rigid as personality structure) that poorer sleep quality and higher levels of daytime sleepiness too influence scores on Past Negative and Future Negative (Rönnlund, Michael and Carelli, Maria G (2018). Hence, it is logical to verify if TPs can be manipulated to help one overcome uncertainty. In business and politics, it is observed that people are feeling uncertainty of future deeply that they feel totally rounded-up by hurdles or caught within a Chakra Vyuh (wheel form strategy of surrounding the enemy from all side). This is the juncture, in which one loses hope and even commit suicide. For Example, Pierre Berégovoy of France, Alan Garcia Perez of Peru, Kalikho Pul former Chief Minister of Arunachal Pradesh, Kodela Shiva Prasad Rao former speaker of Andhra Pradesh are a few examples among many veteran politicians and chiefs who committed suicide, worldwide. Scientists need to bother about politicians because the society is run by politics and effective politicians are needed for society's well-being.

1.2 Time Perspective is Promising:

Park, In-Jo., Rie, Juil., Kim, Hyang Sook., and Park, Jiyoung (2020) demonstrated that the FTP-based career intervention resulted in increased scores on the Career decision-making, self-efficacy and the Career search self-efficacy among under graduate students. High future time orientation is likely to have high levels of hope and self-regulation.

Time perspective particularly guides people's decisions in relation to subjective importance of perceived utility - more so than the personality dimensions of the five-factor model. Most individuals fit their hope or uncertainty into the events of future and its outcomes. Future Time Perspective is argued to be different from personality with acceptable substantiations (Dorien T. A. M. Kooij., Ruth Kanfer and Matt Betts., Cort W. Rudolph.,2018). High inhibitory control ensures being less biased toward a particular time horizon (Zajenkowski, Stolarski, Maciantowicz, Malesza, & Witowska, 2016), while self-regulation of individuals predicted by Executive functioning, and inhibition in particular (Hofmann, Schmeichel, & Baddeley, 2012). Time horizon is enhancing the self – regulation or self – regulation enhances time perspective, is a question that requires close study.

Time perspective is found to be influencing the incentive value of individuals' motives and thereby determine the self-control (Dreves, Parker A.; and Blackhart, Ginette C, 2019). Particularly related to business, Indirasari, Dyah Triarini., Purba, Debora Eflina., Anindita, Rizka (2019) made significant finding that resilience fully mediated the relationship between future time perspective and turnover intention. That is, Future Time Perspective is dynamically mediated. Future time perspective and resilience have significant positive correlation, while resilience and turnover intention have significant negative correlation. Though resilience is often found to be a positive one, it also does a spoiler work. Hence, an intricate psychological angle related to resilience is to be borne in mind while attempting therapy. It, also, seems that when the individuals are more focused on internal state

(resilience) they tend to value less the external reward (turnover). The future time perspective is to be intricately managed for attaining higher turnover intention.

It is clear so far from these aspects that Time perspective is conceptually independent but functionally intricate. Such junctures can also be taken to substantiate need for a separate branch ‘Intricacy Psychology’ for psychologists to stay highly professional and away from quacks in producing judicious contribution to individuals and society (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022a)

One’s perception of the future is related to set of behaviours and outcomes in different settings such as society, organization, and personal / individual. Such outcomes are over and above big five personality traits (Dorien T. A. M. Kooij., Ruth Kanfer and Matt Betts., Cort W. Rudolph 2018). Higher FTP is shown to enhance adjustments to achieve desirable results such as management of uncertainty (Price et al., 2017). But is it the higher FTP per se or a mediated higher FTP, is to be understood clearly. As already discussed, higher FTP also goes against certain positive needs such as higher turnover intention, that the FTP being handled delicately.

1.3 Some Characteristics of Chakra Vyuha:

Chakra Vyuha (Chakra means Wheel and Vyuha means strategy) will not be known to victim till he is finally rounded up by the total soldiers engaged in chakra Vyuha (being rounded – up / blocked). The victim is distracted and felt as if there is only regular fighting and fail to sense forth coming rounding up by opponents in a wheel form – victim held at the centre of the wheel. Chakra Vyuha uses the principle of prolong, make tired, lead into the depth, and then surround from 360 degrees in the wheel form, with multiple layers of opponents.

Many businessmen and politicians also get into the position of totally being surrounded up by opponents or things against oneself in the same way, gradually without being aware that one is getting trapped into.

In the current paper, author tries to propose the ways that would help one to get out of such a position of being trapped into a chakra Vyuha.

The getting away from the trap is more referred to ensuring a future for oneself by escaping from the trap. One who loses the moral courage or hope while realizing that being trapped, will lose hope of future and becomes demoralized only to get defeated by opponents.

As of now, Time perspective is a tool found to be somewhat helpful to this end.

2. CURRENT EFFORTS

To begin with, current author wanted to study closely, through introspection, the factors that could be understood as manipulating the Future Time Perspective or vice versa. Thus, the current author had an open mind regarding the study and wanted to understand what is at the core.

Current researcher asked the subject who is self-employed married male and aged 43 years, to first answer the Time perspective scale (Zimbardo and Boyd, 1999).

2.1 Introspection of a Subject:

The current author explained the results to the Subject and asked to get clarified if he doesn’t understand or if he has any doubt. Later, the current author asked the Subject to visualize bringing changes in his Time Perspective items on which he has scored more toward negative side.

He was asked to introspect the feel he gets as he imagined attempting to change his selected Time Perspectives. He was asked to narrate the core reaction that was occurring in his mind – including thoughts, images, and emotions.

His introspective report was:

“there was some feel....I could not say as positive.....but something heavy.....as if I am cornered or challenged..... that I may be cornered or challenged in future....the people will look different at me.....like I am doing something odd....suddenly my mind went blinking and elsewhere.....could not say where but there were thoughts going on.....I am not able to say what thoughts.....I am not able to recollect.....like a dream when I try to check that now, what it was like.....i felt enough.....that should be stopped...

Current author probed further based on the introspective report, regarding ‘people will look different at me’, as this was the core of the introspection.

Current author: can you elaborate what did you feel when felt the people will look different at you?

Subject: Yes, I felt so.... (Probably now he understood the question differently)

Current author: O K....

Current author: mmmm. how did you feel when that thought went on in your mind....?

Subject: I felt something different....like they look at me as if they are right and I was not....(here need to be differentiated between feeling inferior,

regulatory focus, self-efficacy, and self-confident factors. Also, the current author wanted to be careful with regard to

Interrogative attention factor, as a qualified psychologist's core task)

Current author: so, you felt they look at you and you were....

Subject: (interrupts) 'yes...when people look at me as if I am different, then it is negative for me...they may avoid....

[Now, the author analyzed his modulation and stressing in his message and clear for any experienced psychologist that it is akin to Regulatory Focus of 'Prevention'.]

Current author: Does it give a kind of uncertainty of future?

Subject: Yes.... I want to clear...I had similar feel in the past and now also.... I wanted to clear in the past, but could not.

Current author: I see...

Subject: Yes Sir.... I also sometimes wished the past best occasions continued.... Good things stop at

a point....and change to odd time...I am thinking whether to consider past good things or future.... Past or future, I feel I want good things.....

Here, a psychologist could understand that the subject wished to "cross the time divisions" viz., past, present and future. Current author feels here another concept, the continued time horizon rather than segregated perception of past, present and future. This needs to be studied in future. This could be more related to the Subject's feel that irrespective of timeline (past or future) the good things (Positive Outcomes) should continue as if on single continuum.

2.2 It is interpreted that:

As an individual thinks regard to business, Time Perspective doesn't operate alone but the Response Continua to this is set based on other factors and especially Regulatory Focus also.

Hence, the Psychologist is needed to consider Time Perspective and Regulatory Focus as a crossing continuum and the individual's 'field' to be plotted before attempting any therapy, if justice to be done to the client. The Regulatory Focus covers Past, Present, and Future Time packed into Future Change. The prevention focus is likely to enhance uncertainty and resistance to change.

So, in case of Resistance to Change in Time Perspectives, qualified Psychologists should consider the Resistance as a 'function of Regulatory Focus'. This juncture to be studied further along with earlier finding that FTP influenced regulatory focus (Kevin T Wynne., Boris Baltes., Daniel Krenn., and Annet De Lange 2014). FTP, Resistance To Change and Regulatory Focus form a triangle.

What is most important is 'Seamless Time Focus' –

an "ability to accept promotion and prevention equally and convert prevention into promotion without leaving it to continue as prevention across the seamless time horizon (without segregating past, present and future)".

The inevitable ingredients – viz.,

- a) accepting promotion and prevention, instead of a compulsion to avoid losses (prevention)

- b) convert prevention, that is instead of putting efforts to avoid losses (as target) targeting the conversion of losses into resources if not profits and hence not showing avoidance of any kind, and
- c) seamless time horizon of not segregating past, present, future and debating which is good or bad but seeing past, present, future on single continua of one's personal life journey – Merged Time Perspective or Seamless Time Horizon.

Once this is occurring, the individual accepts his person (self), environment (with whole bunch of persons, things, events, threats, supports and goals), and single time continua. Hence, he is not distracted. Distraction is the difference between actual stimulation minus his acceptable level of intake of stimulation. In said Fluid Focus, one is as calm as a saint in a turmoil and simultaneously as vigilant as a warrior on the battle ground. This crucial juncture is the one to validate his decisions without getting entangled into emotional biases.

Future need not be given much importance nor the time divisions viz, past, present and future.

Time Focus vs Consequence Focus?

Tomorrow Mr A is going to meet Mr. B. if Mr. B comes today unexpectedly or Mr A happens to call on Mr. B today itself, then the importance goes to the outcome not time (Future). Focusing on Consequence gives more relevant guidance to an individual than the time (past or present or future). Contingency between consequences decide many things than time per se.

3. DISCUSSION

During uncertainty, hope might help by signalling importance, effort, and promoting concrete thinking (Gasper, Karen., Spencera, L.A., and Middlewood, B. L. 2019). But it is more of Promotional Focus than Prevention focus that is preferred. Thus, while helping a politician or businessman who has thoroughly uncertain perception of future (mostly near future itself), only a technique that focuses on improving promotional focus can help.

Time perspective coaching is already attempted (Boniwell, I., Osin, Evgeny., and Sircova, Anna 2014) but using host of techniques.

Future time perspective, support entrepreneurial intentions once business opportunities are identified but should be remembered that positive Future Time perspective has indicated a delicate handling for judicious results. This juncture warrants that only professionally qualified psychologists can handle the sessions, if FTP therapy to be administered.

Thus, the introspection using the current Subject indicated that it is not sufficient to manipulate FTP alone but also the intricate juncture of FTP, Regulatory Focus and resistance To Change.

Compare Fig 1 and Fig 2 to find the differences proposed. This altered framework of the trio of Time Perspective, Regulatory Focus and resistance To Change, further helps to understand the stages to be borne in mind in handling the Time Perspective Therapy by qualified Psychologists.

Intolerance of Uncertainty can be differentiated from hopelessness and the correlation between these two are demonstrable (Demirtas, Ayse Sibel and Yildiz, Banu 2019). This is indicating the route for better Time Perspective Therapy that ensuring the Tolerance / Intolerance of Uncertainty as an individual factor for each individual. Though in Fig 2, the Resistance To Change is placed at the Result point, the Tolerance / Intolerance also to be altered as part of the Chakra Vyuh Usncertainty Therapy.

But a closer analysis of the introspection by the current Subject, indicates that instead of FTP and dividing the time horizon, the human mind attempts 'Seamless Time Horizon or Merged Time perspective' to overcome the resistance to change in a natural and smooth manner. Even Future is not viewed as a single entity as the Pessimism Scale differentiates between Expectations about Future and Feeling about Future (Beck A T et.al 1974). Thus, even dividing time into past, present and future only may not be helpful beyond a rudimentary level for therapeutic purposes.

3.1 Proposed framework of therapy:

For an individual to get out of trap and find the future again, newer perspective taking is essential and working through the barriers set by active opponents is the remedy. Perspective taking that related to Self can even bring improvements in pain management (Yu L, Norton S, McCracken LM, 2017).

Current author has extracted following psychological elements of chakra Vyuha are to be tackled in the therapy:

Individual who is trapped into the Chakra Vyuha has,

– Reflective Self-limiting. That is, how one sees his environment also makes him view himself in the same way. For example, Mr A thinks other people should not smoke. So when Mr A thinks of smoking, he thinks others will look down at him. This is neither unconscious nor always conscious but semi-conscious to readily guides conscious thoughts accordingly like ‘reflection’. He thinks people will look down at him since he thinks of others so, but in reality others may not look down at him. This is not ‘projection mechanism of Freud. *‘The more I limit others in my mind, the more I limit myself’.*

- has unshakeable confidence on his capacity/ strategy / valour
- tendency to deny time / chance availability to revise his plans and perspectives
- no realization that what limitation he perceives of his opponent is current self-limiting (but not ‘projection’ mechanism)
- faith in his success as his own superior talent and denies contribution of opponent’s currently running weaknesses / giving-in.
- perception that his efforts are unilinear and opponents’ efforts are curvilinear – another most devastating reflective limiting.
- most assiduous efforts in proving his past rather than accepting entirely new future.

The probable framework that would be more promising is as follows:

4. CONCLUSIONS

Time Perspective doesn't operate alone but the Response Continua to this is set based on other factors and especially Regulatory Focus also; Psychologist is needed to consider Time Perspective and Regulatory Focus as a crossing continuum and the individual's 'field' to be plotted before attempting any therapy, if justice to be done to the client.

Rather than time factor (such as past, present, future) Consequences Focus is more convincing in attaining positive states.

Merged Time perspective / Seamless Time horizon is proposed in the place of FTP.

A framework for Chakra Vyuha Uncertainty therapy is proposed, that would be beneficial in helping many businessmen and politicians who encounter a situation of being trapped and surrounded by uncertainty / opponents in 360 degrees.

Limitations:

- This paper is theoretical for most part.
- This paper is based on Introspection of an individual Subject.

Recommendations for future:

- This framework to be studied using more individuals as subjects.
- This framework to be studied only by qualified psychologists as many core psychological principles are to be handled in a careful manner.

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